

1 **Therapeutic exercise is effective in reducing the intensity of non-specific low back pain**
2 **in children and adolescents: a systematic review and network meta-analysis**

3 **ABSTRACT**

4 **Objective:** To compare the different physiotherapy treatments and determine the most
5 effective treatment to reduce the non-specific low back pain (NSLBP) intensity in children
6 and adolescents.

7 **Data Sources:** Eight databases (Cochrane Library, MEDLINE, PEDro, Web of Science,
8 LILACS, IBECs, PsycINFO and SCOPUS), and two health-specialized journals (BMJ and
9 Spine) were searched from inception to May 2023, with no language restriction.

10 **Study Selection:** Individuals aged 6 to 18 years with NSLBP were selected, and physical
11 therapy treatments were considered. Studies were required to be controlled clinical trials with
12 pretest and posttest evaluations, and to report pain intensity.

13 **Data Extraction:** Data extraction and risk of bias assessment were performed independently
14 by two reviewers.

15 **Data Synthesis:** A meta-analysis of 11 controlled trials with 827 participants found that
16 physiotherapy treatments effectively reduced NSLBP intensity on posttest measurement ($d_+ =$
17 0.75 , 95% CI= $0.30-1.20$) and six-month follow-up ($d_+ = 0.35$, 95% CI= $-0.72-1.40$). Network
18 meta-analysis showed both therapeutic exercise ($d_+ = 1.11$, 95% CI= $0.48-1.74$) and a
19 combination of therapeutic exercise and manual therapy ($d_+ = 1.45$, 95% CI= $0.40-2.49$) were
20 effective compared to no treatment. There were no significant differences between therapeutic
21 exercise and the combination of therapeutic exercise and manual therapy.

22 **Conclusion:** Physical exercise has proven to be the most effective treatment for addressing
23 the intensity of NSLBP in children and adolescents. While combining it with manual therapy
24 may yield even better results, it is crucial to emphasize that physical exercise should serve as
25 the cornerstone in the physiotherapeutic approach to managing NSLBP intensity in this age

26 group.

27 **Keywords:** Low back pain; Exercise; Children; Adolescent; Meta-analysis; Systematic

28 review

29 **List of abbreviations:** ICC (intraclass correlation coefficient), LBP (low back pain), NMA

30 (network meta-analysis), NSLBP (non-specific low back pain), PRISMA (Preferred

31 Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses, RoB (risk of bias),

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51 INTRODUCTION

52 In recent years, an increase in the prevalence and severity of low back pain (LBP) in children
53 and adolescents has been observed [1], reaching about 39% of lifetime prevalence [2,3], rising
54 to 73.6% in some studies [4]. Furthermore, LBP in adolescence is associated with LBP in
55 adulthood [1]. The effects of LBP may lead to activity limitations and restricted social
56 participation, with an emphasis on school absenteeism and gym or sports participation [2],
57 and this is considered a concern that needs to be addressed [1]. Non-specific low back pain
58 (NSLBP) is the most common form of LBP, as the specific cause is rarely identified [5,6].

59 Physiotherapists employ a variety of modalities to treat NSLBP in children and adolescents.
60 Among them, therapeutic exercise stands out as a well-studied and highly recommended
61 treatment to control the intensity and disability of NSLBP in all age groups [7]. In addition,
62 education emerges as a valuable tool to reduce the intensity of NSLBP in children and
63 adolescents [8]. The combination of exercise and education is advocated, as the synergistic
64 benefits outweigh those achieved when these interventions are employed individually in all
65 age groups [9]. In addition, manual therapy is another effective intervention employed by
66 physical therapists to alleviate the intensity of NSLBP in all age groups [10]. Some
67 researchers propose the involvement of parents or caregivers in the patient's treatment as a
68 beneficial approach [11].

69 There is a large difference between the research activity in the treatment of NSLBP in
70 children and adolescents and in adults [12]. In adults, the various therapeutic approaches for
71 NSLBP have undergone extensive examination, resulting in the formulation of clinical
72 practice guidelines. In contrast, insufficient information is available for children and
73 adolescents, making it difficult to develop corresponding clinical guidelines for NSLBP in
74 this demographic group. [13]. In recent years, a guideline has been published on the treatment

75 of back pain in children and adolescents, but not specific to NSLBP [14]. Therefore,
76 substantial uncertainty remains as to which treatment option should be preferred for NSLBP.
77 Network meta-analysis (NMA) is a statistical technique that allows the results of more than
78 two interventions to be compared [15,16]. This method has been used in systematic reviews
79 on the effectiveness of interventions aimed at reducing NSLBP intensity in adults [17,18] but
80 not in children and adolescents.

81 Given these considerations, updating the knowledge base is essential, as a considerable
82 amount of time has passed since the last meta-analysis, during which new clinical trials have
83 been published. Furthermore, no network meta-analysis has been conducted in this field and
84 population, which suggests that this new analysis could offer insights not captured by
85 traditional meta-analyses [16].

86 Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate whether physiotherapy treatment could
87 decrease the intensity of NSLBP in children and adolescents, and to determine the most
88 effective treatments to achieve this outcome.

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90 **Methods**

91 The current meta-analysis was carried out following the Preferred Reporting Items for
92 Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) statement guidelines in the network meta-
93 analysis extension [19] and registered with PROSPERO (CRD42021267640).

94 **Eligibility criteria**

95 **Type of participants**

96 Participants included in the studies were children and adolescents aged 6 to 18 with NSLBP.
97 Participants with LBP secondary to spinal diseases, surgical vertebral treatment, neurological
98 diseases or other pathologies were excluded.

99 **Type of interventions**

100 The studies had to perform any of the following physiotherapeutic treatments: education,
101 therapeutic exercise or manual therapy, alone or in combination.

102 **Type of outcome measures**

103 The studies needed to include numerical assessments of pain intensity.

104 **Type of study design**

105 Only controlled trials were eligible, with adequate statistical data to calculate effect size
106 (including mean, SD, and the sample size of all groups) and which included pretest and
107 posttest assessments.

108 **Study characteristics**

109 Studies had to have been published or completed at the date of the analysis.

110 **Search strategy**

111 Several methods were used to search for studies: different specialized databases, specialized
112 journals on the subject, and the bibliography of expert authors on the subject were searched.
113 Published and unpublished articles were searched. To ensure comprehensive coverage of
114 relevant studies, we used a range of specialized databases in health sciences in general and in
115 specific disciplines. The different databases were Cochrane Library, MEDLINE, PEDro, Web
116 of Science, LILACS, IBECs, PsycINFO and SCOPUS. The specialized journals used were
117 BMJ, due to its significant impact on pediatric medicine, and Spine, because of its
118 specialization in the field. In the search for unpublished articles, articles by relevant authors,
119 conference acts, and doctoral theses were examined. Besides, the bibliography of articles
120 already collected was also checked. The search was conducted by the corresponding author
121 (JGM) and all researchers jointly decided which studies should be finally included. The
122 detailed search strategy is provided in Supplementary file 1.

123 **Study selection**

124 After the initial search and elimination of duplicates, the corresponding author reviewed the
125 titles and abstracts of the remaining articles. Subsequently, all investigators obtained and
126 evaluated the full articles to determine their inclusion or exclusion. Once all eligible studies
127 were collected from both databases and journals that met the criteria, the references of these
128 included articles were examined for possible studies not captured by the initial database
129 search.

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132 **Data extraction**

133 The data extraction of the articles was carried out based on a previously exposed coding
134 manual. In this manual, according to Lipsey's recommendations [20] the variables were
135 grouped into three different categories: substantive (treatment, context, and participant),
136 methodological, and extrinsic variables. Supplementary file 2 provides a detailed information
137 on the coded variables.

138 Data on all the variables gathered in each individual study were extracted by two authors
139 separately (JGM, ICM). A third author (AGC) intervened to decide the extracted data to
140 resolve discrepancies between the two authors. When required, additional data were requested
141 directly from the corresponding authors.

142 In order to assess the reliability of the coding process, Cohen's Kappa was calculated for
143 qualitative variables and the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) for quantitative variables
144 [21]. Kappa values ranged between 0.8 and 1 and the ICC ranged between 0.914 and 1.

145 **Risk of bias**

146 The Cochrane Risk of Bias 2 tool was used to assess the risk of bias (RoB) [22]. Two authors
147 (JGM and ICM) assessed the risk of bias independently, in case there was no consensus a

148 third investigator (AGC) assessed the final score. The overall RoB was the worst judgment
149 across all domains. In the case of multiple domains where the judgment was "some concern",
150 the overall classification was "high risk of bias", consistent with the guidelines provided by
151 the tool's authors. [22]. Cohen's Kappa was used to assess inter-rater agreement, with a result
152 of 1.

153 **Data synthesis and statistical analysis**

154 To calculate the effect size, a standardized mean difference "*d*" was used for quantitative
155 variables, namely the difference in standardized mean change between treatment groups [23]
156 (equations 6 and 7). The pretest-posttest and pretest-follow up differences were estimated.
157 The effect size was calculated by the first author (JGM) with the supervision of another
158 author (JLL). The magnitude of the *d* index was interpreted following Cohen's
159 recommendations [21]. If the article did not report sufficient data to calculate the effect size
160 and the corresponding author was unable to provide it, the estimates for the standard
161 deviations were approximated [24].

162 A random-effects model was applied for each outcome variable reported in at least two
163 studies [25] using the correction proposed by Hartung [26]. A forest plot with 95%
164 confidence intervals was created to represent numerically and graphically the individual
165 effects of each study, with the average effect size displayed on the bottom section.

166 Heterogeneity was assessed with a prediction interval as well as the I^2 index with the
167 following interpretation: 25% low, 50% medium, and 75% high heterogeneity [27]. To assess
168 potential publication bias, Egger's test [28] and the funnel plot was used for each variable.

169 The moderator variables were analyzed using weighted ANOVA for qualitative variables and
170 meta-regression for numerical variables, both corrected as proposed by Knapp and Hartung
171 [29].

172 In addition to pair-wise meta-analysis, where possible, a NMA was used to compare the effect
173 sizes of different treatments. Moreover, a network plot was created to visualize the data
174 structure. For this purpose, all statistical analyses were performed using R [30] in conjunction
175 with the metafor and network packages [31,32]. The PRISMA checklist was used to check the
176 reporting quality of the meta-analysis [33]. The full PRISMA checklist is shown in
177 Supplementary file 3.

178 **Assessment of the certainty of evidence**

179 The GRADE system was applied to assess the certainty of the evidence [34].

180 **RESULTS**

181 The search strategy collected 25,696 results (Fig.1). After removing duplicates, 20,227 were
182 screened by title and abstract, from which 28 were rated as potentially relevant papers. The
183 articles that were excluded after a review of the body are listed in Supplementary file 4, with
184 the reasons for exclusion. Finally, 11 studies were included in the meta-analysis [35–45].

185 **Study characteristics**

186 The 11 studies collected had an experimental group and a control group [35–45]. In the
187 pretest measurements, the studies comprised 827 children and adolescents with NSLBP,
188 distributed into experimental (n = 411) and control groups (n = 416). In the posttest
189 measurements, the total sample was reduced to 788, divided into 394 in each of the two
190 groups. At follow-up, the total sample was 264, with 140 in the experimental group and 124
191 in the control group.

192 All the studies were composed of boys and girls except three that only included girls
193 [38,39,45]. Two of that three studies were also the only ones that addressed participants with
194 high physical activity (more than 3 hours per week outside the treatment), since the samples
195 were female rowers [38,39]. The studies were comprised of children and adolescents [37,42–

196 44] or only adolescents [35,36,38–41,45] with a mean age from 12 [37] to 18.04 [43] years. In
197 three studies, duration of NSLBP was less than 3 months [37,40,42], more than 3 months in
198 one study [43], and no specified in six studies [35,38,39,41,44,45].

199 The physical therapy treatments used in the experimental groups were therapeutic exercise
200 [35,41,43]; education and therapeutic exercise [37–39,44,45]; therapeutic exercise and manual
201 therapy [40]; and education, therapeutic exercise and manual therapy [36,42]. Control groups
202 were based on therapeutic exercise [40,41,43], education and therapeutic exercise
203 [36,38,42,44], and no intervention [35,37,39,45]. In both groups, the duration of the treatment
204 ranged from 3 weeks [41] to 23 weeks [38,39]. The intensity ranged from 0.75 [37] to 4.16
205 hours per week [41] in the experimental group and from 0.66 [36] to 2.83 hours per week [42]
206 in the control group. The magnitude were from 6 [37] to 31.92 hours [44] in the experimental
207 group and from 8 [36,41] to 34 hours [42] in the control group. The main researcher of all the
208 studies were physiotherapists except two, one was a physical education teacher [35] and other
209 was an ergonomist [45]. The characteristics of the included studies are presented in
210 Supplementary file 5.

211 **Risk of bias**

212 Four studies were considered to be at high RoB, [38–40,44] whereas some concerns were
213 found for seven studies [35–37,41–43,45]. The reasons for the high RoB assessments were
214 high attrition [38,40], and lack of randomization [38,39,44]. All studies were rated as some
215 concerns in the "deviation bias" section because the therapists were aware of the treatment
216 they were applying and to which group they were applying it, and all studies obtained low
217 risk of bias in the "selection of the reported result bias" section. For more details about the
218 RoB, see table 1.

219 **Treatment effectiveness**

220 Synthesis of results – conventional pair-wise meta-analysis

221 The analysis of the intensity of NSLBP in the posttest measurement yielded a mean effect size
222 of $d_+ = 0.75$ (95% CI 0.30-1.20), with $I^2 = 73.92\%$ of the total variability due to
223 heterogeneity. A prediction interval was also calculated (95% CI= -0.53-2.02), revealing large
224 uncertainty with regards to the range of expected effect size values for a future primary study
225 in this area (Fig.2).

226 All studies obtained better results in the experimental groups compared to the control groups.
227 Only three studies obtained statistically significant differences compared to the control group
228 (inactive control groups in these studies) [35,39,45]. The study with the smallest effect size
229 compared the same exercise program treatment but a vibroacoustic treatment was added to the
230 experimental group [41]. The second study with the smallest effect size compared an
231 individualized manual therapy and exercise program with a general education program
232 compared to a non-individualized exercise and general education program [36]. All of the
233 studies that performed exercise used strengthening exercises except one [45] and only two did
234 not use stretching exercises [36,43]. All of the studies that carried out education also included
235 knowledge acquisition theoretical and practical except two that only used theory [37,39]. The
236 manual therapy used in three studies were orthopedic manual therapy [36] and manipulation
237 [40,42].

238 The two studies with the longest treatment duration (23 weeks) obtained a moderate-to-high
239 [38] and high [39] effect size and the study with the less weeks of treatment (3 weeks) were
240 the one with the smallest effect size [41]. The study with the most intense treatment (4.16
241 hours per week) was also the study with the smallest effect size [41] and the experimental
242 group with the less intensity (0.75 hours per week) [37] had low-to-moderate effect size.

243 Finally, both the study with the most magnitude (42 hours) [42] and the study with the less
244 magnitude (6 hours) [37] obtained a similar moderate-to-high effect size.

245 Given the specific nature of the studies involving rowing athletes and the potential for
246 different effects compared to the general pediatric population, a sensitivity analysis in the
247 posttest measurement was performed by excluding these two studies [38,39]. The sensitivity
248 analysis yielded an effect size of $d_+ = 0.68$ (95% CI = 0.12-1.24) with a prediction interval
249 between -0.79 and 2.14. This result demonstrated a significant effect in favor of the
250 experimental group, similar to the findings of the primary analysis. Consequently, the
251 exclusion of these studies did not result in a substantial change in the effect size, indicating
252 that the presence of athlete-specific studies did not significantly impact the overall results of
253 the analysis.

254 Since the Jones (2007) study [35] reported an effect size of $d_+ = 2.5$, a sensitivity analysis by
255 excluding this study to assess its impact on the overall effect size and the funnel plot was
256 performed. The effect size for this additional analysis was $d_+ = 0.59$ (95% CI = 0.34-0.83)
257 with a prediction interval between 0.05 and 1.12. Although this effect size was lower than that
258 observed in the primary analysis, the change in magnitude is small and the statistical
259 conclusion remained the same, suggesting that exclusion of this study did not substantially
260 alter the overall findings.

261 The analysis of the intensity of NSLBP in the follow-up obtained a mean effect size of $d_+ =$
262 0.35 (95% CI= -0.72-1.43) with $I^2 = 57.31\%$ of the total variability due to heterogeneity
263 (Fig.3). Only three studies performed measurements at follow-up [37,40,42] with no
264 statistically significant differences between experimental and control groups in the NSLBP
265 intensity. All studies evaluated the follow-up at 6 months [37,40,42] and one an additional
266 evaluation at 12 months [42] after started treatment. The analysis was conducted using the

267 data from the 6 months of all studies for greater homogeneity. One study obtained non-
268 significant differences in favor of the control group at follow-up although it obtained non-
269 significant differences in favor of the experimental group at posttest. This study carried out
270 education and therapeutic exercise, however, this education was only theoretical and it was
271 also the only study with an inactive control group at follow-up [37]. One study did not share
272 information about the number of weeks of treatment, intensity and magnitude [40]. One study
273 yielded statistical significance, with a medium size effect estimate of $d_+ = 0.70$ (95% CI=
274 0.22-1.18) at 6 months but not at 12 months (95% CI= -0.03-0.94) [42]. This study performed
275 therapeutic exercise, education and manual therapy with the highest weeks of treatment,
276 intensity and magnitude of the three studies [42].

277 Analyzing moderator variables

278 For the variable NSLBP intensity, moderating variables were examined based on the clinical
279 judgments of the authors. Due to the small number of studies, the number of moderating
280 variables analyzed was limited to the posttest evaluation.

281 For qualitative moderating variables, weighted ANOVAs were used. Those studies that
282 incorporated education as part of their treatment in the experimental group obtained a larger
283 effect size than those that did not, although without statistically significant differences (p
284 =.22). Likewise, studies with a high risk of bias yielded effects that were on average not
285 statistically different from the studies rated as some concerns ($p =.81$). For more details, see
286 Table 2.

287 Table 3 shows the continuous moderating variables analyzed by meta-regression. Treatment
288 intensity yielded a non-significant effect ($b_j = 0.318$, 95% CI= -0.756-0.12). Similarly,
289 treatment magnitude showed a non-significant association with the effect sizes ($b_j = -0.02$,
290 95% CI= -0.070-0.029). Mean age also demonstrated a non-significant effect ($b_j = 0.116$, 95%

291 CI= -0.686-0.918), and the percentage of females yielded a non-significant association ($b_j = -$
292 0.0006, 95% CI= -0.027-0.026).

293 Other valuable analyses could have included examining the socioeconomic status and
294 educational background of the participants. However, only two studies provided this
295 information, which was insufficient to examine their association with effect size magnitude.
296 The reported variables were tobacco use [42], as well as parental education and the presence
297 of parents with LBP [44].

298 Publication bias

299 To assess publication bias, Egger's test and a funnel plot were performed. In the result of
300 Egger's test was non-significant ($p = .95$), whereas no clear indication of publication bias was
301 observed in the funnel plot (Fig. 4).

302 Regarding the sensitivity analysis conducted without the Jones (2007) study [35], the funnel
303 plot showed increased homogeneity, as the outlier was no longer present. This revised funnel
304 plot can be found in Supplementary file 6. Additionally, Egger's test for this analysis resulted
305 in a p-value of 0.7671, which was not significant, consistent with the primary analysis. These
306 results suggested that there was no evidence of publication bias.

307 Synthesis of results – network meta-analysis

308 Pain intensity outcomes

309 Due to the heterogeneity of the different treatments, the comparisons were grouped into the
310 following treatments: therapeutic exercise [35–37,39,40,42,45], therapeutic exercise + manual
311 therapy [36,40,42], and no treatment [35,37,39,45] (Fig.5).

312 As Figure 5 shows, therapeutic exercise was compared to no treatment and therapeutic
313 exercise + manual therapy in one or more primary studies, however, no treatment was not

314 directly compared to therapeutic exercise + manual therapy in any study. Compared to no
315 treatment, both therapeutic exercise $d_+ = 1.11$ (95% CI= 0.48-1.74) and therapeutic exercise +
316 manual therapy $d_+ = 1.45$ (95% CI= 0.40-2.49) obtained statistically significant differences.
317 When comparing therapeutic exercise to therapeutic exercise + manual therapy, a non-
318 significant difference of $d_+ = 0.33$ (95% CI= -1.78-1.11) in effect size was obtained in favor
319 of therapeutic exercise + manual therapy (Fig.6).

320 **Certainty of evidence**

321 Following the GRADE System, a moderate quality of evidence was found. More details are
322 available in Supplementary file 7.

323 **DISCUSSION**

324 A systematic review with pair-wise and network meta-analysis was conducted to compare
325 different physiotherapy treatments on the intensity of NSLBP in children and adolescents. In
326 the past decade, both systematic reviews about spinal manual therapy in pediatric patients
327 [46,47] and traditional meta-analyses about physical therapy treatments in NSLBP in children
328 and adolescents [48,49] without follow-up analysis had been published. Since then, several
329 new primary studies were published. This is the first NMA comparing different physical
330 therapy treatments in NSLBP in this population. The results of this NMA provide insights
331 into the current state of the evidence on the effectiveness of physical therapy on pain intensity
332 in NSLBP, as well as the different treatment strategies that have been examined so far.

333 The results support that physical therapy treatments are effective in reducing the intensity of
334 NSLBP in children and adolescents at post-test $d_+ = 0.75$ (95% CI= 0.30-1.20), and at 6-
335 month follow-up $d_+ = 0.35$ (95% CI= -0.72-1.43). These results are in line with other meta-
336 analyses that also obtained significant results in the post-test in favor of physical therapy
337 [48,49]. No previous meta-analysis performed follow-up analyses due to the lack of studies.
338 In the post-test, our (pair-wise) meta-analysis yielded a larger effect size than previous meta-

339 analysis that also included case studies $d_+ = 0.50$ (95% CI= 0.19-0.80) [49], but also obtained
340 a smaller effect size than another meta-analysis that only analyzed two studies $d_+ = -2.87$
341 (95% CI= -4.14-(-1.60)) in favor of therapeutic exercise vs control group [48]. Many of the
342 studies that were analyzed in these previous meta-analyses have also been analyzed in the
343 current study [35–39]. The only study with statistically significant results at follow-up
344 performed education, therapeutic exercise and manual therapy [42], so opting for this strategy
345 for the long term could be promising.

346 The instruments used to obtain pain intensity in the studies are diverse: Visual Analog Scale,
347 Numeric Pain Rating Scale, and unspecified 0-10 scales. Therefore, a homogenization of pain
348 measurement would be advisable for future studies in the field.

349 Regarding moderator analyses, in addition to the analyses that could be performed, it would
350 have been valuable to include socioeconomic and environmental variables, as these factors
351 have been shown to influence this population [50,51]. However, there was insufficient data
352 available to conduct such analyses.

353 In addition to the consolidation of the effects of physical therapy treatments in the reduction
354 of NSLBP intensity, the main contribution of this NMA is the comparisons between
355 treatments. Therapeutic exercise added to manual therapy showed slightly better results than
356 manual therapy alone, although the difference was not statistically significant. Manual
357 therapy seems to be more effective in adolescents than in children [47], even though the
358 results are generally inconsistent [14,47]. This indicates that the effect of manual therapy is
359 limited. Therefore, manual therapy should always be used as a complementary treatment
360 rather than the primary approach.

361 Additionally, it was not possible to compare the effect of education separately, since all
362 studies that examined it included it in combination with other treatment components, mainly

363 therapeutic exercise. This may be due to the fact that in recent years it has been argued that
364 exercise and education are mutually indissoluble and it seems that there is no interest in
365 comparing the effects of education separately [9,14]. The combination of education and
366 therapeutic exercise may be recommended as education can be an enhancer of therapeutic
367 exercise by improving goal awareness and having a clearly defined therapeutic objective [52].
368 However, given the small number of studies available for each treatment type, this analysis
369 was not conducted under optimal conditions. Consequently, the results of the network meta-
370 analysis should be interpreted with caution.

371 Concerning the types of therapeutic exercise, there is a notable prevalence of strengthening
372 and stretching exercises compared to other types. All studies, except one [45], employed
373 strengthening exercises, and all studies, except two, incorporated stretching [36,43].

374 Generally, strengthening exercises target the abdominal, lumbar and lower limb muscles,
375 while stretching focuses primarily on the entire posterior back muscles and the hamstring
376 area. Although a comprehensive analysis comparing various therapeutic exercises is not
377 feasible based on the gathered evidence, it can be asserted that both strengthening and
378 stretching exercises prove the most effective in reducing the intensity of NSLBP.

379 **Study limitations**

380 This study has several strengths. Exhaustive manual and electronic searches were performed,
381 with clearly defined inclusion and exclusion criteria and a thorough extraction process. State-
382 of-the-art statistical analyses were used, and this also applies to risk of bias and quality of
383 evidence assessment tools. In addition, this is the first NMA on this subject in this population,
384 which allowed us to find results that were previously unknown. Regarding limitations, our
385 capacity to perform a comprehensive meta-analysis was limited by the restricted number of
386 available clinical trials. The lack of sufficient data posed a challenge in comparing treatments

387 and impaired our ability to draw meaningful conclusions. Furthermore, all included studies
388 had some concerns or high risk of bias. In addition, there was evidence of high heterogeneity
389 in the effect size of the primary outcome.

390 **Conclusion**

391 Therapeutic exercise has been proven to be effective, and it is recommended that physical
392 therapists prioritize therapeutic exercise as the cornerstone of their treatment approach for
393 reducing pain intensity in cases of NSLBP in children and adolescents. Among therapeutic
394 exercises, lumbar strengthening and stretching exercises are widely recognized as the most
395 common and beneficial.

396 **Ethical approval:** Not applicable.

397 **Declaration of interest:** none.

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579

Suppliers:

Not applicable.

Figure legends:

Figure 1. Flow of studies through the review of all searches.

Figure 2. Forest plot for LBP intensity in the posttest measurement.

Figure 3. Forest plot for LBP intensity in the follow-up measurement.

Figure 4. Funnel plot of effect sizes for measures of LBP intensity in the posttest.

Figure 5. Network plot for LBP intensity.

Figure 6. Summary network meta-analysis results for each treatment compared with no treatment for pain intensity.

Table legends:

Table 1. Risk of bias scores of included studies.

Table 2. Results of the weighted ANOVAs for the LBP intensity measures in the posttest, taking qualitative moderator variables as independent variables.

Table 3. Results of the simple meta-regressions for the LBP intensity and magnitude measures, taking continuous moderator variables as predictors.

Table 1. Risk of bias scores of included studies.

<i>Study</i>	<i>Randomisation bias</i>	<i>Deviations bias</i>	<i>Missing outcome data bias</i>	<i>Outcome measurement bias</i>	<i>Selection of the reported result bias</i>	<i>Overall bias</i>
Jones 2007 ³⁵	+	?	+	?	+	?
Ahlgvist 2008 ³⁶	+	?	+	+	+	?
Fanucchi 2009 ³⁷	+	?	+	?	+	?
Thorpe 2009 ³⁸	-	?	-	+	+	-
Perich 2011 ³⁹	-	?	+	+	+	-
Selhorst 2015 ⁴⁰	+	?	-	+	+	-
Dudoniene 2016 ⁴¹	+	?	+	+	+	?
Evans 2018 ⁴²	+	?	+	+	+	?
Jung 2020 ⁴³	+	?	+	+	+	?
Vitman 2021 ⁴⁴	-	?	+	?	+	-
Heidarimoghadam 2022 ⁴⁵	+	?	+	?	+	?

+ = low risk of bias; ? = some concerns risk of bias; - = high risk of bias

Table 2. Results of the weighted ANOVAs for the LBP intensity measures in the posttest, taking qualitative moderator variables as independent variables.

Variable	<i>k</i>	<i>d</i> ₊	95% CI		ANOVA results
			LL	LU	
Education in e. group:					<i>F</i> (1,4) = 2.07, <i>p</i> = .22
No	4	0.3367	-0.163	0.898	
Yes	3	0.731	0.323	1.139	
Risk of bias:					<i>F</i> (1,8) = 0.021, <i>p</i> = .81
Some concerns	7	0.725	0.128	1.297	
High	4	0.825	-0.030	1.680	

k = number of studies. *d*₊ = mean coefficient alpha. LL and LU = lower and upper 95% confidence limits for *d*₊. *F* = Knapp-Hartung's statistic for testing the significance of the moderator variable. e = experimental group

Table 3. Results of the simple meta-regressions for the LBP intensity and magnitude measures, taking continuous moderator variables as predictors.

Predictor variable	<i>k</i>	<i>b_j</i>	<i>CI.LL</i>	<i>CI.UL</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Time of treatment per week (intensity)	9	-0.318	-0.756	0.12	2.955	.13
Total time of treatment (magnitude)	9	-0.020	-0.070	0.029	0.957	.36
Age of the sample	7	0.1160	-0.6866	0.9185	0.1380	.72
Percentage of females	10	-0.0006	-0.0272	0.0260	0.0025	.96

k = number of studies. *b_j* = regression coefficient of each predictor. *CI.LL* = confidence interval of lower limit. *CI.UL* = confidence interval of upper limit. *F* = Knapp-Hartung's statistic for testing the significance of the predictor (the degrees of freedom for this statistic are 1 for the numerator and *k* – 2 for the denominator). *p* = probability level for the *F* statisti

Search strategy

Title: Therapeutic exercise is effective in reducing the intensity of non-specific low back pain in children and adolescents: a systematic review and network meta-analysis

<i>Database</i>	<i>Search strategy</i>	<i>Number of studies included</i>
<i>Medline</i>	(adolescent* OR child* OR youn* or school*) AND (“back pain” OR “low back pain” OR back complaint* OR “back care”) AND (treatment OR intervention or education OR “postural hygiene” OR “posture education” OR “back function” OR physiotherapy OR ergonomics OR “physical therapy” OR “physical therapy modalities” OR exercise OR “exercise therapy” OR “exercise movement techniques” OR “pain management” OR “pain perception” or chiropractic OR “physical fitness” OR “movement techniques” OR acupuncture OR “acupuncture analgesia” OR massage OR “spinal manipulation” OR rehabilitation OR “back school” OR “conservative treatment” OR recuperation OR “musculoskeletal manipulations” OR “pain measurement” OR “Transcutaneous Electric Nerve Stimulation” OR “Electric Stimulation Therapy”) Filters: age 6-18 Results: (7,289)	Jones ³⁵ , Ahlqwist ³⁶ , Fanucchi ³⁷ , Perich ³⁹ , Selhorst ⁴⁰ , Vitman ⁴⁴
<i>Web of Science</i>	(adolescent* OR child* OR youn* or school*) AND (“back pain” OR “low back pain” OR back complaint* OR “back care”) AND (treatment OR intervention or education OR “postural hygiene” OR “posture education” OR “back function” OR physiotherapy OR ergonomics OR “physical therapy” OR “physical therapy modalities” OR exercise OR “exercise therapy” OR “exercise movement techniques” OR “pain management” OR “pain perception” or chiropractic OR “physical fitness” OR “movement techniques” OR acupuncture OR “acupuncture analgesia” OR massage OR “spinal manipulation” OR rehabilitation OR “back school” OR “conservative treatment” OR recuperation OR “musculoskeletal manipulations” OR “pain measurement” OR “Transcutaneous Electric Nerve Stimulation” OR “Electric Stimulation Therapy”) Filters: All Databases, Topic Results: 14,780	Dudoniene ⁴¹ , Evans ⁴² , Heidarimoghadam ⁴⁵
<i>Cochrane Library</i>	(adolescent* OR child* OR youn* or school*) AND (“back pain” OR “low back pain” OR back complaint* OR “back care”) AND (treatment OR intervention or education OR “postural hygiene” OR “posture education” OR “back	Jung ⁴³

	function" OR physiotherapy OR ergonomics OR "physical therapy" OR "physical therapy modalities" OR exercise OR "exercise therapy" OR "exercise movement techniques" OR "pain management" OR "pain perception" or chiropractic OR "physical fitness" OR "movement techniques" OR acupuncture OR "acupuncture analgesia" OR massage OR "spinal manipulation" OR rehabilitation OR "back school" OR "conservative treatment" OR recuperation OR "musculoskeletal manipulations" OR "pain measurement" OR "Transcutaneous Electric Nerve Stimulation" OR "Electric Stimulation Therapy")	
	Filters: none Results: 2,110	
<i>PEDro</i>	Adolescent* "low back pain"	0
	Filters: Match all search items (AND) Results: 19	
<i>PsycInfo</i>	(adolescent* OR child* OR youn* or school*) AND ("back pain" OR "low back pain" OR back complaint* OR "back care") AND (treatment OR intervention or education OR "postural hygiene" OR "posture education" OR "back function" OR physiotherapy OR ergonomics OR "physical therapy" OR "physical therapy modalities" OR exercise OR "exercise therapy" OR "exercise movement techniques" OR "pain management" OR "pain perception" or chiropractic OR "physical fitness" OR "movement techniques" OR acupuncture OR "acupuncture analgesia" OR massage OR "spinal manipulation" OR rehabilitation OR "back school" OR "conservative treatment" OR recuperation OR "musculoskeletal manipulations" OR "pain measurement" OR "Transcutaneous Electric Nerve Stimulation" OR "Electric Stimulation Therapy")	0
	Filters: School-age (6-12 years), Adolescent (13-17 years) Results: 233	
<i>LILACS</i>	Adolescent* AND "low back pain"	0
	Filters: none Results: 172	
<i>IBECS</i>	Adolescent low back pain	0
	Filters: match all the search items (AND) Results: 5	
<i>SCOPUS</i>	(adolescent* OR child* OR youn* or school*) AND ("back pain" OR "low back pain" OR back complaint* OR "back care") AND (treatment OR intervention or education OR "postural hygiene" OR "posture education" OR "back function" OR physiotherapy OR ergonomics OR "physical	0

therapy” OR “physical therapy modalities” OR exercise OR
“exercise therapy” OR “exercise movement techniques” OR
“pain management” OR “pain perception” or chiropractic OR
“physical fitness” OR “movement techniques” OR
acupuncture OR “acupuncture analgesia” OR massage OR
“spinal manipulation” OR rehabilitation OR “back school” OR
“conservative treatment” OR recuperation OR
“musculoskeletal manipulations” OR “pain measurement” OR
“Transcutaneous Electric Nerve Stimulation” OR “Electric
Stimulation Therapy”)

Filters: Title-Abstract-Keywords

Results: 1,088

Citation search: 0

Therapeutic exercise is effective in reducing the intensity of non-specific low back pain in children and adolescents: a systematic review and network meta-analysis

The following treatment features were coded: (a) the type of physiotherapy treatment (education, therapeutic exercise, manual therapy, others); (b) the acquisition mode of education (acquisition of knowledge, posture training habits, body awareness training, others); (c) the teaching method of postural hygiene (theoretical, practical); (d) the type of therapeutic exercise (stretching, strengthening, pelvic tilt exercises, breathing, posture correction, balance exercises, others); (e) the duration of the treatment (in weeks); (f) the intensity of the treatment (number of weekly hours of treatment received by each subject); (g) the magnitude of the treatment (total number of hours received by each subject); (h) the existence of an established number of sessions; (i) the homogeneity of the treatment (whether all patients received the treatment in the same conditions); (k) the inclusion of homework; (k) the inclusion of a follow-up program; (l) the use of external agents to the therapeutic group (subjects that are not part of the therapy group, who are not professionals, but who have an influence, being able to support the subjects in attaining their therapy goals); (m) the presence of family members who act as co-therapists that continue or carry out preventive treatment at home); (n) the presence of teachers who act as co-therapists that continue or carry out preventive treatment at home; (o) the mode of application of the intervention (direct, indirect or mixed); (p) the mode of training (group, individual or mixed); (q) the use of informed consent. Regarding the characteristics of the therapists the following variables were coded: (r) the number of therapists; (s) whether or not the authors agree with the therapists; (t) the training of the therapist (physiotherapist, other); (u) the experience of the therapists (large, medium, low, mixed), and (v) the gender of therapists (men, women, mixed).

Only two contextual characteristics were coded: (a) the country and (b) the place where the intervention was carried out (university, clinic, health center/day center, hospital, school, sports center, mixed).

The participant characteristics coded in the samples of each study were: (a) the mean age of the subjects and the standard deviation (SD) (in years); (b) the gender of the sample (percentage of males); (c) the physical activity level of subjects during the intervention (low, moderate, regular), (d) the mean duration of pain (months), (e) whether or not they had undertaken previous treatments, and (f) the percentage of participants with spinal deformity.

The following methodological characteristics were coded: (a) how the subjects were allocated to the treatments (randomly vs. nonrandomly); (b) the type of control group (nonactive vs. active); (c) the largest follow-up in the study (in months); (d) the sample size; (e) the attrition in the posttest; (f) the attrition in the follow-up; (g) the attrition difference in the posttest and; (h) the attrition difference in the follow-up.

Finally, the extrinsic characteristics coded were: (a) the year of the study; (b) the profession of the first author (physiotherapist, ergonomist, teacher, physician, other), (c) the publication of the study (published vs. un published) and, (d) the publication source (paper, book chapter, book or monograph, unpublished manuscript, congress communication, technical report, doctoral thesis, and others).

PRISMA NMA Checklist of Items to Include When Reporting A Systematic Review Involving a Network Meta-analysis

Section/Topic	Item #	Checklist Item	Reported on Page #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review <i>incorporating a network meta-analysis (or related form of meta-analysis)</i> .	1
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary including, as applicable: Background: main objectives Methods: data sources; study eligibility criteria, participants, and interventions; study appraisal; and <i>synthesis methods, such as network meta-analysis</i> . Results: number of studies and participants identified; summary estimates with corresponding confidence/credible intervals; <i>treatment rankings may also be discussed. Authors may choose to summarize pairwise comparisons against a chosen treatment included in their analyses for brevity.</i> Discussion/Conclusions: limitations; conclusions and implications of findings. Other: primary source of funding; systematic review registration number with registry name.	1
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known, <i>including mention of why a network meta-analysis has been conducted</i> .	3,4
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of questions being addressed, with reference to participants, interventions, comparisons, outcomes, and study design (PICOS).	4
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists and if and where it can be accessed (e.g., Web address); and, if available, provide registration information, including registration number.	4
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify study characteristics (e.g., PICOS, length of follow-up) and report characteristics (e.g., years considered, language, publication status) used as criteria for eligibility, giving rationale. <i>Clearly describe eligible treatments included in the treatment network, and note whether any have been clustered or merged into the same node (with justification)</i> .	4,5
Information sources	7	Describe all information sources (e.g., databases with dates of coverage, contact with study authors to identify additional studies) in the search and date last searched.	5

Search	8	Present full electronic search strategy for at least one database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	Supplementary Table 1
Study selection	9	State the process for selecting studies (i.e., screening, eligibility, included in systematic review, and, if applicable, included in the meta-analysis).	Figure 1
Data collection process	10	Describe method of data extraction from reports (e.g., piloted forms, independently, in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	6
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought (e.g., PICOS, funding sources) and any assumptions and simplifications made.	Supplementary file 2
Geometry of the network	S1	Describe methods used to explore the geometry of the treatment network under study and potential biases related to it. This should include how the evidence base has been graphically summarized for presentation, and what characteristics were compiled and used to describe the evidence base to readers.	6,7
Risk of bias within individual studies	12	Describe methods used for assessing risk of bias of individual studies (including specification of whether this was done at the study or outcome level), and how this information is to be used in any data synthesis.	6,7
Summary measures	13	State the principal summary measures (e.g., risk ratio, difference in means). <i>Also describe the use of additional summary measures assessed, such as treatment rankings and surface under the cumulative ranking curve (SUCRA) values, as well as modified approaches used to present summary findings from meta-analyses.</i>	6,7
Planned methods of analysis	14	Describe the methods of handling data and combining results of studies for each network meta-analysis. This should include, but not be limited to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Handling of multi-arm trials;</i> • <i>Selection of variance structure;</i> • <i>Selection of prior distributions in Bayesian analyses; and</i> • <i>Assessment of model fit.</i> 	6,7
Assessment of Inconsistency	S2	Describe the statistical methods used to evaluate the agreement of direct and indirect evidence in the treatment network(s) studied. Describe efforts taken to address its presence when found.	6,7
Risk of bias across studies	15	Specify any assessment of risk of bias that may affect the cumulative evidence (e.g., publication bias, selective reporting within studies).	6,7
Additional analyses	16	Describe methods of additional analyses if done, indicating which were pre-specified. This may include, but not be limited to, the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitivity or subgroup analyses; • Meta-regression analyses; • <i>Alternative formulations of the treatment network; and</i> • <i>Use of alternative prior distributions for Bayesian analyses (if applicable).</i> 	6,7

RESULTS†

Study selection	17	Give numbers of studies screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally with a flow diagram.	8
Presentation of network structure	S3	Provide a network graph of the included studies to enable visualization of the geometry of the treatment network.	Figure 5
Summary of network geometry	S4	Provide a brief overview of characteristics of the treatment network. This may include commentary on the abundance of trials and randomized patients for the different interventions and pairwise comparisons in the network, gaps of evidence in the treatment network, and potential biases reflected by the network structure.	9,10
Study characteristics	18	For each study, present characteristics for which data were extracted (e.g., study size, PICOS, follow-up period) and provide the citations.	8,9
Risk of bias within studies	19	Present data on risk of bias of each study and, if available, any outcome level assessment.	9
Results of individual studies	20	For all outcomes considered (benefits or harms), present, for each study: 1) simple summary data for each intervention group, and 2) effect estimates and confidence intervals. <i>Modified approaches may be needed to deal with information from larger networks.</i>	8,9 Supplementary file 5
Synthesis of results	21	Present results of each meta-analysis done, including confidence/credible intervals. <i>In larger networks, authors may focus on comparisons versus a particular comparator (e.g. placebo or standard care), with full findings presented in an appendix. League tables and forest plots may be considered to summarize pairwise comparisons. If additional summary measures were explored (such as treatment rankings), these should also be presented.</i>	9,10,11,12
Exploration for inconsistency	S5	Describe results from investigations of inconsistency. This may include such information as measures of model fit to compare consistency and inconsistency models, <i>P</i> values from statistical tests, or summary of inconsistency estimates from different parts of the treatment network.	11
Risk of bias across studies	22	Present results of any assessment of risk of bias across studies for the evidence base being studied.	8,9, table 1
Results of additional analyses	23	Give results of additional analyses, if done (e.g., sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression analyses, <i>alternative network geometries studied, alternative choice of prior distributions for Bayesian analyses, and so forth</i>).	11
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	24	Summarize the main findings, including the strength of evidence for each main outcome; consider their relevance	14,15

		to key groups (e.g., healthcare providers, users, and policy-makers).	
Limitations	25	Discuss limitations at study and outcome level (e.g., risk of bias), and at review level (e.g., incomplete retrieval of identified research, reporting bias). <i>Comment on the validity of the assumptions, such as transitivity and consistency. Comment on any concerns regarding network geometry (e.g., avoidance of certain comparisons).</i>	16,17
Conclusions	26	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence, and implications for future research.	17
FUNDING			
Funding	27	Describe sources of funding for the systematic review and other support (e.g., supply of data); role of funders for the systematic review. This should also include information regarding whether funding has been received from manufacturers of treatments in the network and/or whether some of the authors are content experts with professional conflicts of interest that could affect use of treatments in the network.	17

Therapeutic exercise is effective in reducing the intensity of non-specific low back pain in children and adolescents: a systematic review and network meta-analysis

Studies excluded

Research design were not RCT or Non-RCT

1. Epps SV, Zempsky W, Schechter N, Pescatello LS, Lerer T. The Effects of a Two-Week Trial of Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation for Pediatric Chronic Back Pain. *Journal of Pain and Symptom Management*. 2007;34(2):115–7.
2. Cañeiro JP, Ng L, Burnett A, Campbell A, O’Sullivan P. Cognitive Functional Therapy for the Management of Low Back Pain in an Adolescent Male Rower: A Case Report. *Journal of Orthopaedic & Sports Physical Therapy*. 2013;43(8):542–54.
3. Walston Z, Yake D. Lumbar Thrust Manipulation and Exercise for the Treatment of Mechanical Low Back Pain in Adolescents: A Case Series. *J Orthop Sports Phys Ther*. 2016;46(5):391–8

Participants were adults

1. Glomsrød B, Lønn JH, Soukup MG, Bø K, Larsen S. ‘Active back school’, prophylactic management for low back pain: three-year follow-up of a randomized, controlled trial. *J Rehabil Med*. 2001;33(1):26–30.
2. Lena O, Gil JLM, Todri J, Santiago ABG. The effectiveness of mézières therapy in the athletes with low back pain: the case study of national rhythmic gymnastics team of Murcia. *Revista INFAD de Psicología International Journal of Developmental and Educational Psychology*. 2017;4(1):229–40.

Participants had other diseases that can cause LBP

1. Scoliosis
 1. Zapata KA, Wang-Price SS, Sucato DJ, Thompson M, Trudelle-Jackson E, Lovelace-Chandler V. Spinal Stabilization Exercise Effectiveness for Low Back Pain in Adolescent Idiopathic Scoliosis: A Randomized Trial. *Pediatr Phys Ther*. 2015;27(4):396–402.
 2. Atici Y, Aydin CG, Atici A, Buyukkuscu MO, Arikan Y, Balioglu MB. The effect of Kinesio taping on back pain in patients with Lenke Type 1 adolescent idiopathic scoliosis: A randomized controlled trial. *Acta Orthop Traumatol Turc*. 2017;51(3):191–6.
 3. Zapata KA, Wang-Price SS, Sucato DJ. Six-Month Follow-up of Supervised Spinal Stabilization Exercises for Low Back Pain in Adolescent Idiopathic Scoliosis. *Pediatr Phys Ther*. 2017;29(1):62–6.
2. Hemophilia
 1. Azab AR, Elnaggar RK, Diab RH, Moawd SA. Therapeutic value of kinesio taping in reducing lower back pain and improving back muscle endurance in adolescents with hemophilia. *J Musculoskelet Neuronal Interact*. 2020;20(2):256–64
3. Spondylolysis

1. Selhorst M, Rodenberg R, Padgett N, Fischer A, Ravindran R, MacDonald J. An Alternative Model of Care for the Treatment of Adolescent Athletes with Extension-Based Low Back Pain: A Pilot Study. *IJSPT*. 2021;16(1):227–35.

Did not report LBP intensity data

1. Ng L, Cañeiro JP, Campbell A, Smith A, Burnett A, O’Sullivan P. Cognitive functional approach to manage low back pain in male adolescent rowers: a randomised controlled trial. *Br J Sports Med*. 2015;49(17):1125–31.
2. Dissing KB, Hartvigsen J, Wedderkopp N, Hestbæk L. Conservative care with or without manipulative therapy in the management of back and/or neck pain in Danish children aged 9-15: a randomised controlled trial nested in a school-based cohort. *BMJ Open*. 2018;8(9):e021358.
3. Poncela-Skupien C, Pinero-Pinto E, Martínez-Cepa C, Zuñil-Escobar JC, Romero-Galisteo RP, Palomo-Carrión R. How does the Execution of the Pilates Method and Therapeutic Exercise Influence Back Pain and Postural Alignment in Children Who Play String Instruments? A Randomized Controlled Pilot Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(20):E7436.
4. Shaygan M, Jaber A. The effect of a smartphone-based pain management application on pain intensity and quality of life in adolescents with chronic pain. *Sci Rep*. 2021 Mar 23;11(1):6588.

Did not report enough data to calculate effect size

1. Harringe ML, Nordgren JS, Arvidsson I, Werner S. Low back pain in young female gymnasts and the effect of specific segmental muscle control exercises of the lumbar spine: a prospective controlled intervention study. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc*. 2007;15(10):1264–71.
2. Candy EA, Farewell D, Jerosch-Herold C, Shepstone L, Watts RA, Stephenson RC. Effect of a high-density foam seating wedge on back pain intensity when used by 14 to 16-year-old school students: a randomised controlled trial. *Physiotherapy*. 2012;98(4):301–7.
3. Kovácsné Bobály V, Szilágyi B, Makai A, Koller Á, Járomi M. Improvement of lumbar motor control and trunk muscle conditions with a novel low back pain prevention exercise program. *Orv Hetil*. 2017;158(2):58–66.

Table 1. Characteristics of the studies included.

Study	Country	Design	Participants	Intervention	Intervention descriptions	Intervention duration	Main results
Jones 2007 ³⁵	England	RCT	E n = 31 Age (SD) = 14.6 (0.6) % Male = NA	Therapeutic exercise	Stretching + Strengthening + Stabilisation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cat stretch, knees to chest and knees to side + Horizontal side support on knees, bent knee curl-ups and single legs extensions holds (superman) + Horizontal side support, single leg and contra-lateral arm extension holds 	8 weeks, 1 hour per week, 8 total hours	A specific therapeutic exercise program reduced the intensity of LBP statistically significantly in adolescents. The no intervention group had worse pain intensity in their post-test assessment. In the comparison between both groups, the therapeutic exercise group obtained significant differences compared to the no intervention group.
			C n = 31 Age (SD) = 14.6 (0.5) % Male = NA	No intervention	No intervention		
Ahlqwist 2008 ³⁶	Sweden	RCT	E n = 23 Age (SD) = 15 % Male = 34.78	Education + Therapeutic exercise + Manual therapy	Knowledge acquisition + Strengthening + Coordination + Resistance + Manual therapy + Stationary bicycle	12 weeks	Both individualized and non-individualized therapeutic exercise program with general education obtained significant results in their post-test evaluation. Comparing both groups, the individualized therapeutic exercise with general education and manual therapy obtained better results with no significant differences between them.
			C n = 22 Age (SD) = 14 % Male = 27.27	Education + Therapeutic exercise	Knowledge acquisition + Brisk walks + Running + bicycle + Swimming	12 weeks, 0.66 hours per week, 8 total hours	

Fanucchi 2009 ³⁷	South Africa	RCT	E n = 39 Age (SD) = 12 (0.7) % Male = 61.53	Education + Therapeutic exercise	Knowledge acquisition (theoretical) + Stretching + Strengthening + Pelvic Scale + Breathing + Postural correction + Balance + Functional exercises + Warm-up + Relaxation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explanation of the core musculature, correct posture, and spinal alignment + Hamstring, lumbar spine iliopsoas and quadriceps stretches + Core activation (transverse abdominis, pelvic floor muscles and bridge with progression) + Pelvic tilt + Diaphragmatic breathing + Postural alignment and progressions in four-point kneeling + Balance exercises (one leg: eyes open, eyes closed; and leg swinging) + Functional exercises (side lunges, "apple picking" squats, and mini squats on one leg) + Warm up (breathing exercises, trunk rotation, cat and camel stretches) + Relaxation (relaxed in supine with breathing exercises) 	8 weeks, 0.75 hours per week, 6 total hours	An education and therapeutic exercise program reduced the intensity of LBP in children and adolescents at post- treatment evaluation and 6 months follow-up. Control group did not reduce the pain intensity at post-test evaluation but did at 6-months follow-up. Experimental group obtained better results in the post-test evaluation. Control group obtained better results at 6-months follow-up. There were not statistical differences between them in any measurement.
			C n = 33 Age (SD) = 12 (0.7) % Male = 45	No intervention	No intervention		
Thorpe 2009 ³⁸	Australia	Non- RCT	E n = 17 Age (SD) = 13.9 (0.9) % Male = 0	Education + Therapeutic exercise	Knowledge acquisition + Stretching + strengthening + Coordination + Running (Hill running) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic spinal mechanics, injury risk in rowing, potential LBP mechanisms in rowing, spinal posture education, attitudes and LBP management + Stretching + Back muscles endurance 	23 weeks, 1.16 hours per week, 26.66 total hours	The inclusion of strengthening, stretching and coordination back muscles exercises to the therapeutic exercise program resulted in non- significant improvements in

LBP intensity in adolescents.

			<p>C n = 13 Age (SD) = 13.8 (1) % Male = 0</p>	<p>Education + Therapeutic exercise</p>	<p>Knowledge acquisition + Running (Hill running)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic spinal mechanics, injury risk in rowing, potential LBP mechanisms in rowing, spinal posture education, attitudes and LBP management + Hill running 	<p>23 weeks</p>	
Perich 2011 ³⁹	Australia	Non-RCT	<p>E n = 33 Age (SD) = 14.7 (1.1) % Male = 0</p>	<p>Education + Therapeutic exercise</p>	<p>Knowledge acquisition (theoretical) + Stretching + Strengthening + Coordination + Running (Hill running)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education on basic spinal mechanics, injury risk, mechanisms of LBP, spinal posture whilst sitting, rowing and lifting, and management of LBP + Flexibility training + Strength + Hill running 	<p>23 weeks, 1.14 hours per week, 26.17 total hours</p>	<p>A therapeutic exercise program composed by stretching, strengthening, coordination and aerobic exercise in conjunction with education significantly reduced the intensity of LBP in adolescent female rowers.</p>
			<p>C n = 42 Age (SD) = 14.4 (0.9) % Male = 0</p>	<p>No intervention</p>	<p>No intervention</p>		
Selhorst 2015 ⁴⁰	United States	RCT	<p>E n = 18 Age (SD) = 14.7 (1.15) % Male = 29.4</p>	<p>Therapeutic exercise + Manual therapy</p>	<p>Stretching + Strengthening + Postural correction + Functional exercises + Stabilization + Manipulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stretching + Core strengthening + Postural training + High-level functional exercises + Lumbar stabilization + Lumbar manipulation 	<p>4 weeks</p>	<p>Both groups obtained better results in their post-test and 6-months follow-up measurements. The addition of manipulation to treatment resulted in non-significant</p>

			C n = 13 Age (SD) = 15 (1.41) % Male = 47.1	Therapeutic exercise	Stretching + Strengthening + Postural correction + Functional exercises + Stabilization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stretching + Core strengthening + Postural training + High-level functional exercises + Lumbar stabilization + Sham lumbar manipulation 	4 weeks	improvements in LBP intensity at post-treatment evaluation and at 6-month follow-up in adolescents.
Dudoniene 2016 ⁴¹	Lithuania	RCT	E n = 20 Age (SD) = 13-18 % Male = NA	Therapeutic exercise	Strengthening + Stabilization + Vibroacoustic therapy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core trunk stabilization exercises + Vibroacoustic therapy 	3 weeks, 4.16 hours per week, 13.33 total hours	Both groups obtained significant improvements in the post-test evaluations. Adding vibroacoustic therapy to this program resulted in a non-significant improvement.
			C n = 20 Age (SD) = 13-18 % Male = NA	Therapeutic exercise	Strengthening + Stabilization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core trunk stabilization exercises 	3 weeks, 2.5 hours per week, 8 total hours	
Evans 2018 ⁴²	United States	RCT	E n = 93 Age (SD) = 15.5 (1.6) % Male = 30.1	Education + Therapeutic exercise + Manual Therapy	Knowledge acquisition + Postural habits training + Body awareness training + Stretching + Strengthening + Warm-up + Manipulation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-care education (patient-centered goal setting and emphasis on the importance of movement and activity, pain management and spinal posture awareness with basic activities of daily living) + Stretching + Strengthening (bridge, abdominal crunches, quadruped, side bridge and back extensions) + Light aerobic warm up + High-velocity and low amplitude spinal manipulation 	12 weeks, 3.5 hours per week, 42 total hours	Both groups obtained improvement in the decrease of LBP intensity in children and adolescents at post-test, 6-months follow-up and 12-months follow-up. Adding manual therapy obtained non-significantly better results at post-treatment evaluation and at 12-months follow-up but obtained significantly better

			C n = 92 Age (SD) = 15.3 (1.8) % Male = 32.6	Education + Therapeutic exercise	Knowledge acquisition + Postural habits training + Body awareness training + Stretching + Strengthening + Warm-up <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-care education (patient-centered goal setting and emphasis on the importance of movement and activity, pain management and spinal posture awareness with basic activities of daily living) + Stretching + Strengthening (bridge, abdominal crunches, quadruped, side bridge and back extensions) + Light aerobic warm up 	12 weeks, 2.83 hours per week, 34 total hours	results at 6-months follow-up.
Jung 2020 ⁴³	South Korea	RCT	E n = 25 Age (SD) = 18 (0.65) % Male = 60	Therapeutic exercise	Strengthening + Warm up + Stabilization + Vibrating platform <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Single bridge, bridge and knee flex, plank or squat, bridge and side bridge (all exercises in a vibrating platform) 	12 weeks, 1.5 hours per week, 15 total hours	Both groups obtained statistically significant differences in the post-test measurement. Experimental group obtained non-significant better results compared to a trunk stabilization program without a vibrating platform in the reduction of LBP intensity in children and adolescents.
			C n = 25 Age (SD) = 18.04 (0.68) % Male = 52	Therapeutic exercise	Strengthening + Warm up + Stabilization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Single bridge, bridge and knee flex, plank or squat, bridge and side bridge 	12 weeks, 1.5 hours per week, 15 total hours	
Vitman 2021 ⁴⁴	Israel	RCT	E n = 12 Age (SD) = 10-18 % Male = NA	Education + Therapeutic exercise	Knowledge acquisition + Body awareness + Stretching + Strengthening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biomechanical and ergonomic principles + Body awareness + Upper limb and spine stretches using a foam roller, cobra stretch, hamstring stretch, upper back stretch, global stretches + Half squat, complete squat, stand on one-foot, lower limb strengthening from a knight's stance, abdominal and gluteal strengthening (bridge), oblique strengthening 	12 weeks, 2.66 hours per week, 31.92 total hours	Both groups obtained statistically significant differences in the post-test measurement. Increased treatment time and intensity, together with individualized exercises, had better non-significant results in reducing LBP intensity in children and adolescents at 12 weeks of treatment compared to a

			C n = 21 Age (SD) = 10-18 % Male = NA	Education + Therapeutic exercise	Knowledge acquisition + Body awareness + Stretching + Strengthening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biomechanical and ergonomic principles + Body awareness + Standard exercises for stretching and strengthening 	12 weeks, 1.91 hours per week, 23 total hours	treatment without individualized exercises and lower treatment time and intensity.
Heidarimo ghadam 2022 ⁴⁵	Iran	RCT	E n = 100 Age (SD) = 14.2 (0.94) % Male = 0	Education + Therapeutic exercise	Knowledge acquisition + Postural habits training + Body awareness training + Stretching + Postural correction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online and face-to-face sessions about ergonomics in daily life and interactions, knowledge of spinal anatomy, musculoskeletal disorders and LBP. Stretching exercises at home and postural correction. 	10 weeks, 2 hours per week, 20 total hours	An exercise program based on stretching, postural correction, and education, has been shown to significantly reduce pain intensity in adolescent females.
			C n = 100 Age (SD) = 14.2 (0.95) % Male = 0	No intervention	No intervention		

n = sample size, E = experimental group, C = control group, SD = Standard Deviation, RCT = Randomized Controlled Trial, NA = not available

Funnel plot of the sensitivity analysis without the Jones (2007) study [35].

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Question: What are the most effective physical therapy treatments to reduce pain intensity?

Bibliography: Brignardello-Petersen R, Bonner A, Alexander PE, Siemieniuk RA, Furukawa TA, Rochweg B, et al. Advances in the GRADE approach to rate the certainty in estimates from a network meta-analysis. J Clin Epidemiol. 2018;93:36–44.

Direct estimate

- Estimate: d_+ 0.75, 95% IC 0.30 to 1.20

1. Risk of bias: serious
2. Inconsistency: not serious
3. Indirectness: not serious
4. Publication bias: undetected

Moderate ⊕⊕⊕○

Indirect estimate

1. Therapeutic exercise vs Therapeutic exercise + Manual Therapy

Moderate ⊕⊕⊕○(due risk of bias)

2. Therapeutic exercise vs No treatment

Moderate ⊕⊕⊕○(due risk of bias)

Intransitivity: not serious

Network estimate

1. Highest between direct and indirect: moderate
2. Incoherence: not serious
3. Imprecision: not serious
4. Final network rating: moderate
5. Most credible estimate: network